

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D2.2 CONFIDENTIAL NETWORKING TOOLKIT

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AKE	Authenticated Key Exchange
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
BSF	Binding Support Function
CBC	Cipher Block Chaining
CBOM	Cryptographic Bill of Materials
DDH	Decisional Diffie-Hellman
DH	Diffie-Hellman
DSA	Digital Signature Algorithm
ECDH	Elliptic Curve Diffie Hellman
ECDHE	Elliptic Curve Diffie Hellman Ephemeral
ECDSA	Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm
ECIES	Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme
FG	Find-Guess
FIPS	Federal Information Processing Standards
FO	Fujisaki-Okamoto
FORS	Forest Of Random Subsets
G,H	Hash Functions
gNB	Next Generation Node B
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HQC	Hamming Quasi-Cyclic
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IND-CCA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Ciphertext Attack
IND-CPA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Plaintext Attack
IND-qCCA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Ciphertext Attack with q de-capsulation queries
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
KDF	Key Derivation Function
KEM	Key Encapsulation Mechanism
LAN	Local Area Network
LWE	Learning With Errors
MCC	Mobile Country Code
MDPC	Moderate Density Parity-Check
MLWE	Module-Learning With Errors
ML-DSA	Module-Lattice-Based Digital Signature Algorithm
ML-KEM	Module-Lattice-Based Key Encapsulation Mechanism
MSIN	Mobile Subscription Identification Number
NF	Network Function
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NRF	Network Repository Function
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NTRU	N-th degree Truncated polynomial Ring Units
NTT	Number Theoretic Transform
NUC	Next Unit of Computing

Abbreviation	Definition
OPRF	Oblivious Pseudo-Random Function
OW-CPA	One-Way Chosen Plaintext Attack
OWE	One-way Encryption
PCF	Policy Control Function
PDU	Packet Data Unit
PFS	Perfect Forward Secrecy
PKE	Public Key Encryption
PKI	Public key infrastructure
PPT	Probabilistic Polynomial Time
PQ	Post-Quantum
PQC	Post-Quantum Cryptography
PRF	Pseudo-Random Function
QC-LDPC	Quantum-safe Low-Density Parity-Check
QC-MDPC	Quantum-safe Moderate Density Parity-Check
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
QROM	Quantum Random Oracle Model
RAN	Radio Access Network
RLWE	Ring Learning With Errors
ROM	Random Oracle Model
RSA	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman System
SBI	Service Based Interface
SE	Symmetric Encryption
SHA	Secure Hash Algorithm
SHAKE	Secure Hash Algorithm and KECCAK
SLH-DSA	Stateful Hash-Based Digital Signature Algorithm
SMF	Session Management Function
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SUPI	Subscription Permanent Identifier
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane Function
WOTS+	Winternitz One-Time Signature Plus
WPFS	Weak Perfect Forward Secrecy
XMSS	eXtended Merkle Signature Scheme

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Executive Summary

This document investigates PQ-secure security *protocols* for 6G. It thus extends Deliverable 2.1, which concentrates on PQ-secure *building blocks* like public key encryption. The focus is on authenticated key exchange (AKE) protocols that can be used to derive secure session keys over insecure networks. Once such a session key has been obtained, symmetric cryptography can be used to exchange messages. This is useful since symmetric algorithms can generally counter quantum attackers by moderately increasing the key size and are very efficient. This methodology does not transfer to (asymmetric) AKE protocols, on the other hand, and thus novel PQ techniques have to be introduced. The document consists of two main parts.

In the first part, we provide a conceptual contribution that has the potential to generally improve the efficiency of AKE protocols if they are based on PQ-secure public-key encryption systems, like those submitted and standardized by NIST after their global competition. As an application, we specifically focus on the winner of that competition Kyber.CCAKEM that will see widespread adoption in the near-future. Our improvement leads to considerable computational savings and thus saves valuable resources while at the same time increasing overall efficiency.

In contrast, the second part of this deliverable is less conceptually and more practically oriented. It encompasses three subparts, each focussing on a different practical aspect around PQC. Firstly, we experimentally benchmark PQ-secure versions of TLS 1.3 in realistic settings with the goal of understanding if PQC poses limitations to existing 5G infrastructure and whether design choices need to be made as we move on to 6G systems. Additionally, we provide an update on the status of standardization efforts around PQC, up to and including NIST's signature onramp. Lastly, we provide concrete strategies and priorities for the migration to PQC, including a number of "no-regret" moves that organisation can adopt now – most prominently, to start with and inventory fo cryptographic assets.

1 Introduction

This document will investigate the space of possible successors of post quantum (PQ) secure security protocols and in particular PQ-secure variants of TLS (i.e. the Transport Layer Security protocol) secure while having the migration strategy of 2.1 in mind. The first part of this document will detail a conceptual contribution consisting of a new way to construct PQ-secure authenticated key exchange (AKE) protocols. AKE protocols allow two remote parties to securely exchange a common symmetric session key of an insecure network. AKE protocols will be the main application scenario for the finalists of NIST's PQ competition. In contrast to the more simple building blocks of public key encryption/key encapsulation mechanisms and digital signatures, AKE protocols combine several primitives and protect against powerful network attackers that could also modify (replay, drop, inject) messages on transit or corrupt parties. The well-known TLS protocol, a cornerstone of modern digital infrastructure, is a famous example of such an AKE protocol.

As our main idea, presented in Section 2, we propose to base AKE protocols on Kyber.CPAPKE instead of Kyber.CCAKEM (the winner of the NIST competition that fulfills the strong security notion of IND-CCA security), exploiting that Kyber.CCAKEM has been constructed in a modular fashion as also detailed in Deliverable 2.1. In particular, Kyber.CCAKEM is the result of the application of the so-called Fujisaki-Okamoto transform to the public key encryption system Kyber.CPAPKE that only fulfills the weak notion of IND-CPA security. While IND-CPA security is generally not enough in many practical applications, we propose to use it in AKE protocols to derive fresh session keys. As we show, in these scenarios, IND-CPA security is often sufficient. As a result, we can improve the overall efficiency of key exchange protocols based on Kyber by making considerable computational savings. Assuming that encryption and decryption in Kyber.CPAPKE requires roughly the same amount of computations, this can essentially halve the time to decrypt ciphertexts and save valuable resources. Moreover, we note that this will not require additional implementations: due to its modular construction, whenever cryptographic libraries implement Kyber.CCAKEM they implicitly also implement Kyber.CPAPKE so the algorithms of Kyber.CPAPKE are readily available on future systems. We stress that while our practical focus is on Kyber.CCAKEM, our idea can be applied much more broadly. This is because virtually all PQ-secure encryption systems follow the same generic design approach, building an IND-CCA secure KEM system from an IND-CPA secure PKE system.

Section 4 details the second main contribution of this deliverable, providing experiments and tests of key exchange protocols in realistic settings. We investigate the implications of using experimental TLS versions that are based on post-quantum algorithms. We describe practically testing and benchmarking various post-quantum algorithms that are supported by available open source post-quantum based TLS libraries. In particular, we describe tests and experiments of experimental post-quantum TLS versions in a lab setup of 5G networks. To this end, different post-quantum algorithms are integrated into TLS running in the 5G network and their performances are analysed.

In Section 5, we provide an up-to-date overview of different standardization efforts in the space of post-quantum cryptography. The bulk of the section focuses on the leading efforts by NIST, covering the standardization of hash-based signature schemes, the main standardization effort that led to three standards being released in the summer of 2024, the ongoing Round 4 that spawned from the main effort and the more recent new competition that is aimed specifically at standardizing additional digital signature schemes. We end the section by summarizing several other standardization efforts, i.e. not led by NIST.

Finally, Section 6 presents several strategies and priorities around the migration to PQC. We start by providing several "no-regret" moves: efforts that any organisation can take now that are useful even leaving aside the quantum threat. The most important no-regret move is the start of an inventory of cryptographic assets. We also provide several priorities for the migration to PQC

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as relevant to 5G/6G networks.

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2 Efficiency Improvements for PQ-Secure AKE Protocols

This section starts by introducing the necessary building blocks and definitions to precisely describe our contribution.

| 2.1 Public Key Encryption

A Public Key Encryption (PKE), also known as asymmetric encryption, is a cryptographic primitive that allows data to be encrypted using a public key and decrypted with a private key. It consists of four polynomial-time algorithms $\text{PKE} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$. Let λ be the security parameter of a PKE, we define the syntax of the algorithms as follows.

- $\text{par} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$: the probabilistic setup algorithm takes as input the security parameter λ in unary and it outputs global system parameters par that define the public key space \mathcal{PK} , the secret key space \mathcal{SK} , the plaintext message space \mathcal{M} and the ciphertext space \mathcal{C} .
- $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})$: the probabilistic key generation algorithm takes as input par and outputs a public key $\text{pk} \in \mathcal{PK}$ and a secret key $\text{sk} \in \mathcal{SK}$.
- $\text{ct} \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m)$: the probabilistic encryption algorithm takes as input a public key $\text{pk} \in \mathcal{PK}$ and a plaintext $m \in \mathcal{M}$, and outputs a ciphertext $\text{ct} \in \mathcal{C}$.
- $m := \text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \text{ct})$: the deterministic decryption algorithm takes as input a secret key $\text{sk} \in \mathcal{SK}$ and a ciphertext $\text{ct} \in \mathcal{C}$, and outputs a plaintext $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

For convenience, we do not explicit the input par for the algorithms Enc and Dec .

We use δ to parameterize correctness.

Definition 2.1 (Correctness PKE). We say that $\text{PKE} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ is δ -correct if for any $\text{par} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$ we have:

$$\Pr[m = m' \mid (\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par}), \text{ct} \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m), m' = \text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \text{ct})] \geq \delta.$$

Now, we introduce min-entropy. It is used to measure the unpredictability of a random variable. It is particularly important in contexts where randomness is used, such as in key generation or cryptographic protocols.

Definition 2.2 (Min-Entropy of PKE). We say that $\text{PKE} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ has min-entropy μ if:

- It has key min-entropy $\mu' \geq \mu$: for any $\text{pk}' \in \mathcal{PK}$ we have $\Pr[\text{pk} = \text{pk}' : (\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})] \leq 2^{-\mu'}$ for some par .
- It has ciphertext min-entropy $\mu'' \geq \mu$: for any $\text{ct}' \in \mathcal{C}$ we have $\Pr[\text{ct} = \text{ct}' : \text{ct} \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m)] \leq 2^{-\mu''}$ for some $\text{pk} \in \mathcal{PK}$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

| 2.1.1 Ciphertext Indistinguishability

Ciphertext Indistinguishability is an encryption scheme property. Given a ciphertext, that is the encryption of a message randomly chosen among two messages determined by the adversary, this property ensures that an adversary cannot determine which of two possible plaintexts was used to produce that ciphertext. Then, it ensures that ciphertexts do not leak information about the plaintexts, providing a strong level of security for encryption schemes.

We introduce two security definitions: indistinguishability under chosen plaintext attack (IND-CPA) and indistinguishability under chosen ciphertext attack (IND-CCA) (Fig. 1). The first allows

the adversary to query to an encryption oracle; the second is similar to IND-CPA, but now the adversary can query also to a decryption oracle. Obviously, the adversary cannot make a query using the challenge ciphertext. Moreover, IND-CCA is divided into two classes: in IND-CCA1 access to the decryption oracle is given only before that the adversary selects two distinct messages and gives them to the challenger, whereas in IND-CCA2, it is given both before and after, except it cannot use the decryption oracle to decrypt the challenge ciphertext.

The indistinguishability game is defined as follow. An adversary \mathcal{A} (that is a PPT algorithm) selects two distinct messages m_0 and m_1 and gives them to the challenger. The challenger picks a random bit b and encrypts the message m_b and give the challenge ciphertext ct^* to \mathcal{A} . Now the adversary outputs a bit b' and it wins if $b' = b$. An adversary can guess the bit randomly having $1/2$ of success probability. We introduce the definition of advantage.

Definition 2.3. The advantage of an adversary \mathcal{A} against a PKE scheme in the game defined in Fig. 1 is defined as

$$\text{Adv}_{\text{PKE}}(\mathcal{A}) := \left| \Pr[\mathcal{A} \text{ wins}] - \frac{1}{2} \right|.$$

IND-CPA, IND-CCA	ENC(m)
00 $(pk, sk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(par)$	08 $ct \leftarrow \text{Enc}(pk, m)$
01 $(m_0, m_1) \leftarrow \mathcal{A}^{\text{ENC}, \text{DEC}}(pk)$	09 return ct
02 $b \leftarrow \{0, 1\}$	
03 $ct^* \leftarrow \text{Enc}(pk, m_b)$	DEC(ct)
04 $b' \leftarrow \mathcal{A}^{\text{ENC}, \text{DEC}}(pk, ct^*)$	10 if $ct = ct^*$:
05 if $b' = b$:	11 return \perp
06 return 1	12 $m \leftarrow \text{Dec}(sk, ct)$
07 return 0	13 return m

Figure 1: Pseudocode for IND-CPA and IND-CCA for PKEs. The gray boxes highlight the differences.

Whenever we consider the security of a PKE without further specification, we refer to the above IND-CPA notion.

| 2.2 Key Encapsulation Mechanism

In cryptography, a Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) is a primitive that allows to generate a symmetric key using asymmetric algorithms. It consists of four polynomial-time algorithms $\text{KEM} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Encaps}, \text{Decaps})$. Let λ be the security parameter of a KEM, we define the syntax of the algorithms as follows.

- $par \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$: the probabilistic setup algorithm takes as input the security parameter λ in unary and it outputs global system parameters par that define the public key space \mathcal{PK} , the secret key space \mathcal{SK} , the ciphertext space \mathcal{C} and the session key space \mathcal{K} .
- $(pk, sk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(par)$: the probabilistic key generation algorithm takes as input par and outputs a public key $pk \in \mathcal{PK}$ and a secret key $sk \in \mathcal{SK}$.
- $(ct, K) \leftarrow \text{Encaps}(pk)$: the probabilistic encapsulation algorithm takes as input a public key $pk \in \mathcal{PK}$ and outputs a ciphertext $ct \in \mathcal{C}$ and a session key $K \in \mathcal{K}$.
- $K := \text{Decaps}(sk, ct)$: the deterministic decapsulation algorithm takes as input a secret key $sk \in \mathcal{SK}$ and a ciphertext $ct \in \mathcal{C}$, and outputs a session key $K \in \mathcal{K}$.

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Even Encaps and Decaps take as input also the global system parameters par , but for convenience we do not explicit it.

Definition 2.4 (Correctness KEM). We say that $\text{KEM} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Encaps}, \text{Decaps})$ is δ -correct if for any $\text{par} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$ we have:

$$\Pr[K = K' \mid (\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par}), (\text{ct}, K) \leftarrow \text{Encaps}(\text{pk}), K' = \text{Decaps}(\text{sk}, \text{ct})] \geq \delta.$$

Definition 2.5 (Min-Entropy of KEM). We say that $\text{KEM} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Encaps}, \text{Decaps})$ has min-entropy μ if:

- It has key min-entropy $\mu' \geq \mu$: for all $\text{pk}' \in \mathcal{PK}$ we have $\Pr[\text{pk} = \text{pk}' : (\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})] \leq 2^{-\mu'}$ for some par .
- It has ciphertext min-entropy $\mu'' \geq \mu$: for all $\text{ct}' \in \mathcal{C}$ we have $\Pr[\text{ct} = \text{ct}' : (\text{ct}, K) \leftarrow \text{Encaps}(\text{pk})] \leq 2^{-\mu''}$ for some $\text{pk} \in \mathcal{PK}$.

Key Encapsulation Mechanisms are typically analyzed under the IND-CCA security definition (Fig. 2), because it provides a strong guarantee of security against practical cryptographic attacks. Moreover, many cryptographic standards and protocols, such as those developed by NIST, require KEMs to meet certain security criteria, often including IND-CCA security. This ensures interoperability and trust in the security of cryptographic implementations across different systems and applications.

IND-CCA	DEC(ct)
00 $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})$	08 if $\text{ct} = \text{ct}^*$:
01 $(\text{ct}^*, K_0) \leftarrow \text{Encaps}(\text{pk})$	09 return \perp
02 $K_1 \leftarrow \mathcal{K}$	10 $K \leftarrow \text{Decaps}(\text{sk}, \text{ct})$
03 $b \leftarrow \{0, 1\}$	11 return K
04 $b' \leftarrow \mathcal{A}^{\text{DEC}}(\text{pk}, (\text{ct}^*, K_b))$	
05 if $b' = b$:	
06 return 1	
07 return 0	

Figure 2: Pseudocode for IND-CCA for KEMs.

Definition 2.6. We say that a KEM is IND-CCA secure if, for any PPT adversary \mathcal{A} the advantage

$$\text{Adv}_{\text{KEM}}^{\text{IND-CCA}}(\mathcal{A}) := \left| \Pr[\mathcal{A} \text{ wins}] - \frac{1}{2} \right|$$

is negligible.

Whenever we consider the security of a KEM without further specification, we refer to the above IND-CCA notion.

| 2.3 Digital Signature

A digital signature is a cryptographic primitive that enables data to be signed, allowing one party to authenticate itself to another. It consists of four polynomial-time algorithms $\text{SIG} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Ver})$. Let λ be the security parameter of a SIG, we define the syntax of the algorithms as follow.

- $\text{par} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$: the probabilistic setup algorithm takes as input the security parameter λ in unary and it outputs global system parameters par that define the verification key space \mathcal{VK} , the signature key space SIGK , the plaintext message space \mathcal{M} and the signature space \mathcal{S} .

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- $(vk, sigk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})$: the probabilistic key generation algorithm takes as input par and outputs a verification key $vk \in \mathcal{VK}$ and a signature key $sigk \in \mathcal{SIGK}$.
- $\sigma \leftarrow \text{Sign}(sigk, m)$: the probabilistic signing algorithm takes as input a signature key $sigk \in \mathcal{SIGK}$ and a plaintext $m \in \mathcal{M}$, and outputs a signature $\sigma \in \mathcal{S}$.
- $b := \text{Ver}(vk, m, \sigma)$: the deterministic verification algorithm takes as input a verification key $vk \in \mathcal{VK}$, a plaintext $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and a signature $\sigma \in \mathcal{S}$, and outputs a bit $b \in \{0, 1\}$.

For convenience, we do not explicit the input par for the algorithms Sign and Ver .

Definition 2.7 (Correctness SIG). We say that $\text{SIG} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Ver})$ is correct if for any $\text{par} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$ we have:

$$\Pr[b = 1 \mid (vk, sigk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par}), \sigma \leftarrow \text{Sign}(sigk, m), b = \text{Ver}(vk, m, \sigma)] = \beta.$$

If β is not specifically mentioned we assume $\beta = 1$.

Definition 2.8 (Min-Entropy of SIG). We say that $\text{SIG} := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Ver})$ has min-entropy μ if:

- It has key min-entropy $\mu' \geq \mu$: for all $vk' \in \mathcal{VK}$ we have $\Pr[vk = vk' : (vk, sigk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})] \leq 2^{-\mu'}$ for some par .
- It has signature min-entropy $\mu'' \geq \mu$: for all $\sigma' \in \mathcal{S}$ we have $\Pr[\sigma = \sigma' : \sigma \leftarrow \text{Sign}(sigk, m)] \leq 2^{-\mu''}$ for some $sigk \in \mathcal{SIGK}$ and some $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

Definition 2.9. The advantage of a PPT adversary \mathcal{A} against a SIG scheme in the Existential Unforgeability under Chosen Message Attack game (Fig. 3) is defined as

$$\text{Adv}_{\text{SIG}}^{\text{EUF-CMA}}(\mathcal{A}) := \Pr[\mathcal{A} \text{ wins}].$$

<u>EUF-CMA</u>	<u>SIG(m)</u>
00 $(vk, sigk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})$	03 if $m = m^*$:
01 $(m^*, \sigma^*) \leftarrow \mathcal{A}^{\text{SIG}}$	04 return \perp
02 return $\text{Ver}(vk, m^*, \sigma^*)$	05 $\sigma \leftarrow \text{Sign}(sigk, m)$
	06 return σ

Figure 3: Pseudocode for EUF-CMA for SIGs.

| 2.4 Hash Functions

Definition 2.10. (Hash Function) Consider a set $= \{H_t\}_{t=1}^{2^\kappa}$ of hash functions indexed by t where each H_t maps from $\{0, 1\}^*$ to the hash space T . We require that $\log_2(|T|)$ is a polynomial in κ . We say that is collision-resistant if for uniformly random t no PPT attacker can output two distinct string m_1, m_2 , such that $H_t(m_1) = H_t(m_2)$ except with negligible probability.

As is common, we model hash functions as families. We assume that whenever a hash function is used, the key (index) t of the hash function is drawn uniformly random in a global setup algorithm.

| 2.5 Authenticated Key Exchange

Authenticated Key Exchange (AKE) is a process in cryptographic protocols where two parties establish a shared secret key over an insecure communication channel, ensuring that the key is known only to the legitimate parties and that they can verify each other's identities. The primary goals of AKE are confidentiality which ensures that the established key is known only to the intended parties and cannot be intercepted by an eavesdropper, integrity that ensures that the messages exchanged during the key establishment process have not been altered by an attacker, and authentication that verifies the identities of the parties involved to prevent impersonation attacks.

We can thus logically identify two essential components for constructing an AKE: key exchange and authentication. Key exchange can be achieved using a KEM as a cryptographic primitive. For authentication, the traditional approach involves digital signatures, but it is also possible to use a KEM. This alternative is considered because, in a post-quantum context, KEMs currently outperform digital signatures.

In general, AKE does not have a fixed number of rounds to compute a shared secret key. This depends on the security features of AKE and how the scheme tries to achieve them.

| 2.5.1 Forward Secrecy

Perfect Forward Secrecy (PFS) and Weak Perfect Forward Secrecy (WPFS) are concepts in cryptographic protocols designed to protect the confidentiality of past communication sessions even if long-term keys are compromised at some future point in time. PFS ensures that the compromise of long-term private keys does not compromise the security of session keys used in previous communication sessions even if the attacker has been active in these communication sessions. This means that even if an attacker obtains the long-term private key of a server or client, it cannot use it to decrypt past sessions. WPFS, on the other hand, ensures that past session keys remain secure against future compromises of long-term keys, but with a reduced security guarantee as compared to PFS; it allows only attacks from a passive adversary, i.e. an adversary that does not modify the messages exchanged in the rounds.

Note for us: we must have that at the moment when setting the session key in some party, the communication partner is uncorrupted.

| 2.6 AKE Definition

An AKE protocol $\text{AKE} = (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Init}, \text{Resp}, \text{DerL}, \text{DerR})$ consists of six algorithms which are executed interactively by two parties as shown in Figure 6. Let us assume the party which initiates the session (initiator) is P_i and the party which responds to the first message (responder) is P_j . All algorithms are probabilistic except for DerR which is deterministic.

- The setup algorithm Setup is given input the security parameter in unary and outputs public parameters par . In the following, we assume that all other algorithms will implicitly use par as input.
- The key generation algorithm KeyGen computes a random keypair (pk, sk) . The public key is made public.
- The initialization algorithm Init inputs sk_i and the public key pk_j of P_j and outputs a message $I \in \mathcal{M}$ and a state state_i .
- The responder's response algorithm Resp takes as input sk_j, pk_j and a message I . It computes a message $R \in \mathcal{M}$ and a state state_j .
- The algorithm DerL computes the last message F and the session key K_i for P_i . Its input is $\text{sk}_i, \text{state}_i, \text{state}_j$, and a message R .

Figure 4: Running protocol AKE between two parties, based on an IND-CCA secure KEM like Kyber.CCAKEM [12, 50] a signature scheme, and hash function H . Kyber.CCAKEM is based on IND-CPA secure Kyber.CPAPKE. Ciphertexts are decrypted using Decaps (indicated in red) which involves executing the two algorithms Enc and Dec of Kyber.CPAPKE.

- Finally, the algorithm DerR takes as input sk_j , $state_j$ and message F and computes session key K_j for P_j . In the absence of any attacker we should have that $K_i = K_j$ with overwhelming probability.

2.7 AKE Security Definition

In the following let $\ell, d \in \mathbb{N}$ be positive integers (indicating the number of overall parties and overall sessions per party). In the execution environment, we fix a set of ℓ honest parties $P = \{P_1, \dots, P_\ell\}$. Each party P_i has a unique public key pk_i and corresponding secret key sk_i .

Next, the execution environment manages for every $i \in [\ell]$ a bit $\text{corrState}_i \in \{\text{corrupted}, \text{uncorrupted}\}$ that is used to denote the corruption state of the secret key sk_i used by P_i . Additionally, the execution environment uses value $\text{corrTime}_i \in [0, d]$, to store the time of corruption of P_i , each corrTime_i indicating that sk_i was corrupted via the corrTime_i -th query of the adversary. Moreover, the execution environment draws a global bit $b \in \{0, 1\}$, indicating whether or not the attacker will be presented with a real or a random key when making a Test-query (as defined next). The bit b will help to capture single-bit security. As argued in [32], this is the right notion of security when examining tight security reductions in the multi-user setting.

Each honest party P_i can sequentially and concurrently execute the protocol multiple times. This is characterized by a collection of oracles $\{\pi_i^s : i \in [\ell], s \in [d]\}$. Oracle π_i^s behaves as party P_i , carrying out a process to execute the s -th protocol instance with some partner P_j . All oracles of P_i have access to sk_i . Moreover, we assume each oracle π_i^s maintains a list of independent internal state variables as described in Table 1, each of which uses supertext s and subtext i to indicate that it is held by π_i^s . These variables are: exstate_i^s , Pid_i^s , role_i^s , K_i^s , and Transcript_i^s .

Additionally, the execution environment associates to each oracle the variable keyState_i^s which denotes the freshness $\text{keyState}_i^s \in \{\text{exposed}, \text{fresh}\}$ of the session key. The remaining variables are only used by the execution environment. Among these variables, the execution environment

Figure 5: Running protocol AKE between two parties, based on an IND-CPA secure PKE like Kyber.CPAPKE, a signature scheme, and hash function H. Ciphertexts are decrypted using the Dec only as indicated in blue.

Figure 6: Running a key exchange protocol between two parties.

will dedicate uniformly random bits rand_i^s to each oracle. The variables of each oracle π_i^s will be initialized as follows:

- The execution-state exstate_i^s is set to uninitialized.
- The variable keyState_i^s is set to fresh.
- All other variables are set to only contain the special string uninitialized.

We always have that $K_i^s = \text{uninitialized}$ iff π_i^s has not reached accepted-state (yet).

Definition 2.11 (Partnering). Two oracles (π_i^s, π_j^t) are said to be partnered if they share the same transcript $\text{Transcript}_i^s = \text{Transcript}_j^t$ and $\text{Pid}_i^s = j$ and $\text{Pid}_j^t = i$.

Adversarial Model. An adversary \mathcal{A} in our model is a probabilistic algorithm with polynomial running time (PPT), which takes as input the security parameter 1^κ and the public information, and may interact with these oracles by issuing the following queries.

Variable	Description
exstate_i^s	denotes the execution-state of oracle π_i^s , i.e. $\text{exstate}_i^s \in \{\text{uninitialized}, \text{waiting}, \text{accepted}\}$
Pid_i^s	stores the identity of the intended communication partner, i.e. $\text{Pid}_i^s \in P$
role_i^s	denotes the role that P_i assumes in the protocol run: $\text{role}_i^s \in \{\text{uninitialized}, \text{Initiator}, \text{Responder}\}$
K_i^s	stores the session key(s) $\text{K}_i^s \in \mathcal{K} \cup \{\text{uninitialized}\}$
Transcript_i^s	records the transcript of messages sent and received by oracle π_i^s in chronological order, i.e. $T \in \mathcal{M}^3$
state_i^s	is used to store the state information.

Table 1: Internal States of Oracle π_i^s

- $\text{SendNit}(\pi_i^s, j)$: if $\text{exstate}_i^s \neq \text{uninitialized}$ this query aborts. Otherwise, this query calls the algorithm $(I, \text{state}_i) \leftarrow \text{Nit}(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_j)$ and outputs I . Additionally, it sets
 - $\text{exstate}_i^s = \text{waiting}$,
 - $\text{role}_i^s = \text{Initiator}$,
 - $\text{Transcript}_i^s = I$,
 - $\text{state}_i^s = \text{state}$, and
 - $\text{Pid}_i^s = j$.
- $\text{SendResp}(\pi_i^s, j, I)$: if $\text{exstate}_i^s \neq \text{uninitialized}$ this query aborts. Otherwise, this query calls $(R, \text{state}_j) \leftarrow \text{Resp}(\text{sk}_i, \text{sk}_j, I)$ and outputs R . Additionally, it sets
 - $\text{exstate}_i^s = \text{waiting}$,
 - $\text{role}_i^s = \text{Responder}$,
 - $\text{Transcript}_i^s = I, R$,
 - $\text{K}_i^s = K$, and
 - $\text{Pid}_i^s = j$.
- $\text{SendDerL}(\pi_i^s, R)$: if $\text{exstate}_i^s \neq \text{waiting}$ or if $\text{role} = \text{Responder}$ this query aborts. Otherwise, this query calls $(K, F) \leftarrow \text{Der}(\text{sk}_i, \text{state}_i^s, R)$ and outputs F . Additionally, it sets
 - $\text{exstate}_i^s = \text{accepted}$,
 - $\text{Transcript}_i^s := \text{Transcript}_i^s, R, F$, and
 - $\text{K}_i^s = K$.
- $\text{SendDerR}(\pi_i^s, F)$: if $\text{exstate}_i^s \neq \text{waiting}$ or if $\text{role} = \text{Initiator}$ this query aborts. Otherwise, this query calls $K := \text{DerR}(\text{sk}_i, \text{state}_i^s, F)$. Additionally, it sets
 - $\text{exstate}_i^s = \text{accepted}$,

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- $\text{Transcript}_i^s := \text{Transcript}_i^s, F$, and
 - $K_i^s = K$.
- $\text{Corrupt}(i)$: the execution environment returns sk_i and sets $\text{corrState}_i := \text{corrupted}$. Moreover, if this was the w -th overall query of the attacker, the execution environment sets $\text{corrTime}_i := w$. We also say that sk_i is w -corrupted.
 - $\text{RevealKey}(\pi_i^s)$: this oracle will output key K_i^s in case that $\text{exstate}_i^s = \text{accept}$ and abort otherwise. Oracle π_i^s responds to a RevealKey -query with the contents of variable K_i^s and sets $\text{keyState}_i^s = \text{exposed}$. If at the point when an adversary issues this query there exists another oracle π_j^t which is partnered to π_i^s , then $\text{keyState}_j^t = \text{exposed}$ for π_j^t .
 - $\text{Test}(\pi_i^s)$: if the oracle π_i^s has state $\text{exstate}_i^s \neq \text{accept}$, then we abort. If the oracle π_i^s is queried for the first time, a random key $\hat{K}_i^s \leftarrow \mathcal{K}$ is drawn. Finally, K_i is returned, where K_0 is the real key K_i^s and K_1 is the random key \hat{K}_i^s .
 - $\text{Execute}(\pi_i^s, \pi_j^t)$: we define this query for convenience only. This query internally simply calls $I \leftarrow \text{SendInit}(\pi_i^s, j)$, $R \leftarrow \text{SendResp}(\pi_j^t, i, I)$, $F \leftarrow \text{SendDerL}(\pi_i^s, R)$, and $\text{SendDerR}(\pi_j^t, F)$. We also say that this query models a *passive* protocol run between the two oracles π_i^s, π_j^t .

Definition 2.12 (Completeness). We say that a AKE protocol Π is *complete*, if for any two oracles π_i^s, π_j^t that are partnered with $\text{Pid}_i^s = j$ and $\text{Pid}_j^t = i$ and $\text{exstate}_i^s = \text{accept}$ and $\text{exstate}_j^t = \text{accept}$ it always holds that $K_i^s = K_j^t$.

We consider protocols with overwhelming completeness, i.e. where completeness holds with probability $1 - \epsilon$ for some statistically small ϵ .

Definition 2.13 (Security Game). We formally consider a security experiment that is played between an adversary and a challenger. In this game, the challenger implements the collection of oracles $\{\pi_i^s : i \in [\ell], s \in [d]\}$. First, the challenger draws a fair coin $b \in \{0, 1\}$. Next, it generates long-term keypairs $(\text{pk}_i, \text{sk}_i)$ for each party i by drawing each $(\text{pk}_i, \text{sk}_i) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par})$. The adversary may start issuing SendInit , SendResp , SendDerL , Corrupt , RevealKey , Execute , and Test queries. Finally, the adversary outputs a bit b' that indicates its guess of b and terminates.

For the security definition, we need the notion of freshness of oracles.

Definition 2.14 (Oracle Freshness). Let π_i^s be an accepting oracle held by party P_i with intended partner $\text{Pid}_i^s = P_j$. Let π_j^t be an oracle (if it exists), such that π_i^s and π_j^t are partnered. Then the oracle π_i^s is said to be w -fresh for $w \in \mathbb{N}$ if none of the following conditions holds:

- the adversary has either made a $\text{RevealKey}(\pi_i^s)$ query or a $\text{RevealKey}(\pi_j^t)$ query, (if π_j^t exists),
- P_i or P_j is w' -corrupted with $w' \leq w$ and the attacker has been active with respect to π_i^s after query w' ,
- the attacker has made query $\text{Test}(\pi_j^t)$.

Observe that in the above definition, it is only a violation of freshness if the adversary sends attacker messages to π_i^s after P_i has been corrupted. However, even after the corruption of P_i , sending messages to π_i^s that have been constructed by some π_j^t is not considered a violation.

This definition is essential in capturing full PFS as it helps to formalize security even if the attacker sends her own messages to π_i^s . The crucial fact is that whenever those messages have been sent to π_i^s , P_i must not be corrupted – as this would trivially break security: the adversary can easily obtain all secret information needed to compute the session key.

In the following, we provide a general security definition for AKE protocols that captures key indistinguishability.

Definition 2.15 (AKE Security Definition). We say that an adversary A (t, ϵ) -breaks a AKE protocol if the following three conditions are all fulfilled:

1. A runs in time t .
2. When the adversary terminates and outputs a bit b' it always holds:

the w -th query is $\text{Test}(\pi_i^s)$ for some oracle $\pi_i^s \Rightarrow \pi_i^s$ is w -fresh.

3. The probability that b' equals b is bounded by

$$|\Pr[b' = b] - 1/2| \geq \epsilon.$$

If an adversary outputs b' such that $b' = b$ and the above conditions are met, then we say that the adversary *answers the Test-challenge correctly*. We say that the AKE protocol is (t, ϵ) -secure, if there exists no adversary that (t, ϵ) -breaks it. We also simply say AKE is secure if no PPT attacker exists that can (t, ϵ) -break it with polynomial $t = t(\kappa)$ and non-negligible advantage $\epsilon = \epsilon(\kappa)$.

| 2.8 Security Analysis

Theorem 2.1. Assume we are given an IND-CPA secure PKE scheme with overwhelming correctness. Then, the security protocol AKE depicted in Fig. 5 has overwhelming completeness.

Proof. Since the KEM is the only source of non-perfect correctness and since it is assumed to be correct expect with overwhelming probability, we have that the entire protocol has overwhelming completeness in the absence of an attacker. \square

Let us now analyse the security of AKE based on an IND-CPA secure PKE scheme like Kyber.CPAPKE.

Theorem 2.2. Assume we are given an IND-CPA secure PKE scheme with overwhelming correctness that has min-entropy at least λ , where λ is the security parameter. Assume we are given a secure signature scheme and a secure hash function. Then, the security protocol AKE depicted in Fig. 5 is a secure AKE protocol.

Proof. By assumption, we know that except for statistically small probability, we have that the values produced by all the sessions will never correspond to a correctness error of the underlying KEM in the absence of an active attacker. So in the following, we concentrate on the case that this always happens. This is true except for statistically low probability. The proof begins by excluding collisions in the hash function. In particular, the probability of such collisions happening is negligible unless the collision resistance of the hash function can be broken: to see this, assume that in the security game there will at some point be a collision. We can now immediately plugin the security game of the hash function. To this end, we will simply use the hash function key that is provided by the hash challenger. Any collision now will immediately transfer to a collision in the hash game.

In the main steps of the proof, we first guess the tested session π_i^s and (if existent) its partnered session π_j^t . This decreases the success probability by only a polynomial factor since there are only polynomially many sessions and polynomial many parties overall. The resulting success

probability is still non-negligible. Let us first consider case A) where a partnered session π_j^t of π_i^s exists. By definition, its holder P_j must be uncorrupted. Next, the proof considers two subcases. In the first case i), the attacker modifies one of the two messages \tilde{pk} or \tilde{ct} sent by the communicating sessions. Observe that the original messages have high entropy due to the min-entropy of KEM being at least λ , so the probability that they match previous values sent by any session before is statistically low. Next, observe that the protocol guarantees that each communication partner will receive a signature over these two messages from its partner. Via the received signature, each party can now verify if its high entropy message has been received successfully by its communication partner unless a signature has been forged. Moreover, any such attacker can be used to break the security of the signature scheme. As a result, sessions will only accept and use the derived session key if they are sure that their own message has been indeed used by the communication partner to derive the session key. In the absence of signature forgeries, if the attacker modifies any of those two values the sender of the original message will abort. Moreover, the receiver of the modified value will also abort unless the attacker delivers a corresponding valid signature on the modified message as well. This cannot be a replayed signature, because every accepted signature must have been on a fresh value with high min-entropy.

Thus, the only way for an attacker to modify messages and still make the sessions accept and compute a session key is thus by forging a signature since by definition the sender of that message must be uncorrupted at this point in time. However, this would immediately break the security assumption on the signature scheme.

To see this consider the security game of the signature scheme that is now played by the reduction. Here the attacker is given the public key of the signature scheme pk' and the attacker is allowed to make signature queries. Now the reduction first guesses whether the forgery will happen for pk_i or pk_j . In the following assume the forgery will happen for pk_ℓ with $\ell \in \{i, j\}$. This reduces the success probability by a factor of two at most. Next, the reduction will play the game with the AKE attacker playing the role of the challenger except that $pk_\ell := pk'$. Other than that the reduction behaves exactly like the challenger. Whenever the reduction has to generate signatures for P_ℓ it just calls the signature challenger to obtain them. If now finally the attacker outputs a new message \tilde{pk} (or \tilde{ct}) together with a valid signature σ (or σ') over this value, this immediately gives a valid signature forgery (h_1, σ) or (h_2, σ') because we have excluded collisions in the hash function.

Finally, consider the case B) that there is no session partnered to the tested session. However, by definition the intended partner is uncorrupted. As before, since the tested session receives a signature over its fresh high entropy message this will immediately break the security of the signature scheme similar to case A).

We have now excluded any modification of the messages \tilde{pk}, \tilde{ct} . Also we only need to focus on the case where the tested session has a partnered session. In the next step, we argue that the derived key K is indistinguishable from a random key unless the attacker can break the IND-CPA security of the underlying PKE. To this end, we consider a distribution where π_i^s , when tested, always outputs K chosen to be an independent random value (in particular independent of the sent messages). We argue that any attacker that could distinguish this change of distributions can be used to break the IND-CPA security of the PKE scheme. To see this, we assume that the public key pk'' of the IND-CPA game is embedded into the ephemeral public key $\tilde{pk} := pk''$ sent or received by the tested session. Next, we send \tilde{K} to the challenger in the IND-CPA game. The challenger returns ct' and the reduction sets $\tilde{ct} := ct'$. With probability $1/2$, ct' is indeed the encryption of \tilde{K} . Observe that this corresponds exactly to the old distribution. However, with probability $1/2$, ct' is the encryption of a truly random key. This now corresponds exactly to the new distribution. So any attacker that distinguishes the two distributions with probability ϵ can be used to break the IND-CPA security with probability ϵ as well. Finally, observe that the used key K is now always uniformly random and independent of the sent messages. So the attacker can never distinguish it from a random key. Overall the runtime of the reduction is polynomial. This

shows that no polynomial-time attacker can exist that with non-negligible advantage breaks the security of the AKE protocol. \square

| 2.9 Fujisaki-Okamoto Transform

Let us now provide some details on how the original Fujisaki-Okamoto transform works. The transform is used specifically for Kyber.CCAKEM and other PQ IND-CCA secure KEMs are variants of this transform. We only provide detailed information on the original transform since the overall ideas and techniques remain largely consistent in all variants. Details on these variants can be found in [25] and follow-up work.

The work [22] presents a technique to construct an IND-CCA public key encryption scheme from weakly secure public key encryption system and a symmetric encryption scheme, that both fulfill weak security definitions. This technique is known as the Fujisaki-Okamoto (FO) transform. When restricting ourselves to variants that aim to construct KEMs we can essentially neglect the symmetric encryption system.

To describe the original technique we first briefly introduce additional notions. A symmetric encryption (SE) scheme $SE := (\text{Setup}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ is similar to a PKE scheme, the only difference is that SE uses a single secret key, called symmetric key, both for encryption and decryption. Moreover, the encryption algorithm is deterministic and not probabilistic as in PKE.

Now, let $PKE := (\text{Setup}_{PKE}, \text{KeyGen}_{PKE}, \text{Enc}_{PKE}, \text{Dec}_{PKE})$ be a PKE scheme, with two associated sets, \mathcal{M}_{PKE} a message space set and \mathcal{R}_{PKE} a random coin set, and let $SE := (\text{Setup}_{SE}, \text{KeyGen}_{SE}, \text{Enc}_{SE}, \text{Dec}_{SE})$ be a SE scheme, with associated a message space set \mathcal{M}_{SE} and a key space set \mathcal{K}_{SE} . Let $G : \mathcal{M}_{PKE} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_{SE}$ and $H : \mathcal{M}_{PKE} \times \mathcal{M}_{SE} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}_{SE}$ be hash functions. From these primitives is possible to construct a new PKE scheme $PKE' := (\text{Setup}', \text{KeyGen}', \text{Enc}', \text{Dec}')$, with $\mathcal{R}' = \mathcal{M}_{PKE}$ and $\mathcal{M}' = \mathcal{M}_{SE}$, as in Fig. 7.

<u>KeyGen'(par)</u>	<u>Dec'(sk, (c₁, c₂))</u>
00 (pk, sk) \leftarrow KeyGen(par)	08 $\hat{\rho} := \text{Dec}_{PKE}(\text{sk}, c_1)$
01 return (pk, sk)	09 $\hat{r}_2 := G(\hat{\rho})$
<u>Enc'(pk, m)</u>	10 $\hat{m} := \text{Dec}_{SE}(\hat{r}_2, c_2)$
02 $\rho \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_{PKE}$	11 $\hat{r}_1 := H(\hat{\rho}, \hat{m})$
03 $r_1 := H(\rho, m)$	12 if $c_1 = \text{Enc}_{PKE}(\text{pk}, \hat{\rho}; \hat{r}_1)$
04 $r_2 := G(\rho)$	13 $m := \hat{m}$
05 $c_1 := \text{Enc}_{PKE}(\text{pk}, \rho; r_1)$	14 else
06 $c_2 \leftarrow \text{Enc}_{SE}(r_2, m)$	15 $m := \perp$
07 return (c ₁ , c ₂)	16 return m

Figure 7: Hybrid scheme PKE'.

Before introducing the main theorem of [22], we need some definitions.

Definition 2.16. Let $PKE := (\text{Setup}_{PKE}, \text{KeyGen}_{PKE}, \text{Enc}_{PKE}, \text{Dec}_{PKE})$ be a PKE scheme and let \mathcal{A} be an adversary. The advantage of \mathcal{A} against a PKE in the One-way Encryption game is defined as

$$\text{Adv}_{PKE}^{\text{OWE}}(\mathcal{A}) := \Pr[\mathcal{A}(\text{pk}, y) = \text{Dec}(\text{sk}, x) \mid (\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{par}), x \leftarrow \mathcal{M}, y \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x)].$$

We say that adversary \mathcal{A} (t, ϵ)-breaks PKE in the sense of OWE if \mathcal{A} runs in at most time t and achieves $\text{Adv}_{PKE}^{\text{OWE}}(\mathcal{A}) \geq \epsilon$. We say that PKE is (t, ϵ)-secure in the sense of OWE if there is no adversary that (t, ϵ)-breaks PKE in that sense. Of course, any PKE scheme that is IND-CPA secure will also be secure in this security game.

Definition 2.17. Let $\text{PKE} := (\text{Setup}_{\text{PKE}}, \text{KeyGen}_{\text{PKE}}, \text{Enc}_{\text{PKE}}, \text{Dec}_{\text{PKE}})$ be a PKE scheme. For given $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \in (\mathcal{PK}, \mathcal{SK})$, $x \in \mathcal{M}$ and $y \in \{0, 1\}^*$, define

$$\gamma(x, y) = \Pr[y = \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x; h) \mid h \leftarrow \mathcal{R}].$$

We say that PKE is γ -uniform, if, for any $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \in (\mathcal{PK}, \mathcal{SK})$, $x \in \mathcal{M}$ and $y \in \{0, 1\}^*$, $\gamma(x, y) \leq \gamma$.

Definition 2.18. Let $\text{SE} := (\text{Setup}_{\text{SE}}, \text{KeyGen}_{\text{SE}}, \text{Enc}_{\text{SE}}, \text{Dec}_{\text{SE}})$ be a SE scheme and let \mathcal{A} be an adversary. The advantage of \mathcal{A} against a SE in the Find-Guess game is defined as

$$\text{Adv}_{\text{SE}}^{\text{FG}}(\mathcal{A}) := \Pr[\mathcal{A}(\text{guess}, s, y) = b \mid k \leftarrow \mathcal{K}, (x_0, x_1, s) \leftarrow \mathcal{A}(\text{find}), b \leftarrow \{0, 1\}, y \leftarrow \text{Enc}(k, x_b)].$$

We require that, for (x_0, x_1) that \mathcal{A} outputs, $x_0 \neq x_1$ and $x_0, x_1 \in \mathcal{M}$.

As before, we say that adversary \mathcal{A} (t, ϵ) -breaks SE in the sense of FG if \mathcal{A} runs in at most time t and achieves $\text{Adv}_{\text{SE}}^{\text{FG}}(\mathcal{A}) \geq \epsilon$. We say that SE is (t, ϵ) -secure in the sense of OWE if there is no adversary that (t, ϵ) -breaks SE in that sense.

Now with the above definitions we can introduce the main theorem.

Theorem 2.3 ([22]). *Suppose PKE is γ -uniform and (t_1, ϵ_1) -secure according to Definition 2.16. Suppose SE is (t_2, ϵ_2) -secure according to Definition 2.18. Let l_1 and l_2 be the sizes of \mathcal{M}_{PKE} and \mathcal{M}_{SE} respectively. Then the hybrid scheme PKE' is $(t, q_G, q_H, q_D, \epsilon)$ -secure in the sense of IND-CCA in the random oracle model where*

$$t = \min(t_1, t_2) - O((q_G + q_H) \cdot (l_1 + l_2))$$

$$\epsilon = (2(q_G + q_H)\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + 1)(1 - 2\epsilon_1 - 2\epsilon_2 - \gamma - 2^{-l_2})^{-q_D} - 1$$

and q_G, q_H are the number of queries to the random oracle G, H and q_D is the number of queries to the decryption oracle.

| 2.10 Application to Kyber

A variant of the FO transform has been used to prove Kyber.CCAKEM secure. In particular, Kyber is based on an IND-CPA secure PKE with overwhelming correctness. This gives the following result.

Theorem 2.4 ([25, 12, 50]). *Kyber.CCAKEM is an IND-CCA secure KEM with overwhelming correctness that is the result of an application of the FO transform given in Fig. 8 to an IND-CPA secure scheme Kyber.CPAPKE with overwhelming correctness.*

So our protocol AKE could be instantiated with the IND-CPA secure algorithm Kyber.CPAPKE. This has the potential to make considerable savings as opposed to a naïve application of Kyber.CCAKEM in AKE as depicted in Fig. 4. More concretely, we can observe in Fig. 8 that the decapsulation operation in Kyber.CCAKEM is much slower than the decryption in Kyber.CPAPKE. This is because as indicated in Lines 9–12 the receiver always has to re-compute the ciphertext in Kyber.CCAKEM. Assuming that encryption and decryption in Kyber.CPAPKE have comparable computation times, this would double the computations necessary for ciphertext decryption in Kyber.CCAKEM as opposed to Kyber.CPAPKE.

So to conclude, applying Kyber.CPAPKE can speed up computations as opposed to Kyber.CCAKEM in selected AKE protocols like AKE while providing overall security as well.

KeyGen'(par) 00 $(pk, sk) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(par)$ 01 $s \leftarrow \mathcal{M}$ 02 $sk' = (sk, s)$ 03 return (pk, sk)	Decaps'(sk' = (sk, s), c) 08 $m' := \text{Dec}_{\text{CPKE}}(sk, c)$ 09 if $c \neq \text{Enc}_{\text{CPKE}}(pk, m'; G(m'))$ 10 if $m' = \perp$ 11 return $K(s, c)$ 12 else return $K := H(m', c)$
Encaps'(pk) 04 $m \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_{\text{PKE}}$ 05 $c \leftarrow \text{Enc}_{\text{CPKE}}(pk, m; G(m))$ 06 $K := H(m, c)$ 07 return (K, c)	

Figure 8: FO-Transform used to construct Kyber.CCAKEM from Kyber.CPAPKE. G, H are hash functions.

3 Scientific Background on Transport Layer Security

The Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol is an AKE protocol (together with the description of a message exchange mechanism) that is a crucial component of internet security, ensuring privacy and data integrity between communicating applications. Before introducing the description of it, we present a short history of it.

The ancestor of TLS is the Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). The first version of it, SSL 1.0, was developed in the middle of 1990, but due to some security flaws, it was never published. The version SSL 2.0 was released in 1995, but had several significant vulnerabilities, including weak cryptographic algorithms and poor design choices that made it insecure. It was deprecated in 2011 in [58] published by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). SSL 3.0 was released in 1996, it addressed many of the issues of SSL 2.0 and laid the groundwork for future developments. However, it still had vulnerabilities that were discovered over time. It was deprecated in 2015 in [8]. TLS 1.0 was the first version of TLS, specified in [15] in 1999. It was essentially an improved version of SSL 3.0, designed to be more secure and to fix the vulnerabilities found in SSL. TLS 1.1 was specified in [16], it introduced improvements over TLS 1.0, such as protection against Cipher Block Chaining (CBC) attacks and more robust handling of padding errors. Both TLS 1.0 and 1.1 were deprecated in 2021 in [36]. In 2008, TLS 1.2 was published in [17]. This version, which is still used nowadays, supports SHA-256 and more flexible cryptographic algorithm negotiation. In 2018, the last version, TLS 1.3, was released in [48]. It is based on TLS 1.2 specification, but this new version is a major overhaul designed to enhance security and performance. Some of the changes are the simplification of the handshake process, the elimination of outdated and insecure cryptographic algorithms and features and the adoption of more secure and performant algorithms.

As already said, TLS is a protocol designed to provide secure communication over computer networks. It is run between two parties, called client (e.g., a web browser) and server (e.g., a web site), and it provides confidentiality, integrity and authenticity. The process begins with the handshake, where the client and the server establish a secure connection. The client starts sending a ClientHello message to the server which includes the cryptographic algorithms and parameters supported. The server replies with a ServerHello message, selecting the parameters chosen by the server. Next, the server sends its certificate to the client. The client verifies the certificate to ensure it is communicating with the legitimate server. If requested by the server, the client may also send its certificate to the server. Once the certificates are verified, the handshake is finished. Now, both the client and server use the secret exchanged during the handshake,

along with the random values sent in the ClientHello and ServerHello messages, to generate the session keys. These keys are used for encrypting and decrypting the data transmitted during the session.

| 3.1 On Post-Quantum TLS

For the post-quantum migration of TLS, we are more interested in the asymmetric (AKE) part of the protocol (usually called the TLS handshake) and go into more detail.

Currently, in the handshake TLS uses RSA and ECDSA as signature schemes and the DH protocol as a key exchange scheme. Unfortunately, these protocols are not secure against quantum adversaries. We recall the state of security against quantum adversaries of the building blocks used in TLS in Table 2 from [14]. The goal of the cryptography community is to substitute these protocols with new ones, presented to the PQ competition of NIST, that are secure against quantum adversary.

Algorithm	Type	Scheme	Quantum Resistance
AES	Symmetric	Encryption	Larger key sizes needed
SHA-2, SHA-3		Hash Function	Larger output needed
RSA	Asymmetric	Signatures, Key Establishment	No secure
ECDSA, ECDH	Asymmetric	Signatures, Key Exchange	No secure
DSA	Asymmetric	Signatures, Key Exchange	No secure

Table 2: Quantum resistance of standard cryptography [14].

In [6], the authors recall some existing solutions based on the broad literature. We follow [6] to present some of them.

Since the authentication in TLS is based on digital signatures, relying on Table 2 we know that the current signature schemes are not secure in the PQ setting, and thus we need to update them; there are two ways to achieve quantum resistance for digital signature, via a pure post-quantum mechanism or via a hybrid post-quantum solution. The first category is divided in

- Hash based signatures, which includes XMSS and SPHINCS+ [28]. Even if it was not a candidate for the PQ competition of NIST, XMSS has been standardized in parallel with the competition. It provides good performance, but the disadvantage is the difficulty of signing messages in TLS sessions. SPHINCS+ presents very good security, but the main problem is the signature size that limits its application. More details can be found in [45, 51, 53, 54].
- Lattice based signatures, which includes CRYSTALS-Dilithium [33], are based on the MLWE assumption, and Falcon [47], based on NTRU [24]. Compared to ECDSA, they have a similar computation time, but the signature or public key sizes are larger; moreover, Falcon requires floating-point arithmetic that is not always supported. For more details we refer to [18, 46].

Hybrid approaches use a classical *and* a PQ signature in parallel. The combinations tested and supported by TLS are RSA/ECDSA with CRYSTALS-Dilithium/Falcon/SPHINCS+. Tests reveal that these combinations are slightly slower compared to purely post-quantum based authentication [34]. In favor of this method, we have to say that the hybrid approaches have received considerably less attention in the past. While we provide a concise overview here, Section 5 will also present further details on PQ-secure digital signatures and the current standardization process of NIST for signature schemes.

Now, we present some of the existing results for key exchange. The main idea is to replace the DH key exchange mechanism with KEMs. As for the digital signatures, to replace classic key exchange there are purely post-quantum and hybrid post-quantum approaches. Purely post-quantum comprise:

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- Lattice based KEMs include CRYSTALS-Kyber [12, 50] that is based on the MLWE assumption. The performance of TLS using KEMs is generally comparable to classic key exchange already used in TLS [53], even at different security levels [18].
- Code based KEMs include HQC [4] and BIKE [7]. They tend to have a slower computation time as CRYSTALS-Kyber in TLS [18, 57].

For hybrid-based key exchange, three approaches were identified.

- Concatenation, where basically the classical and post-quantum key material are treated as a single element. In [44], the authors study the concatenation between ECDHE and CRYSTAL-Kyber in TLS 1.3; under “ideal network conditions”, the performance is equal to a key exchange with ECDHE.
- Separation, where messages are modified or extensions are created to transport additional post-quantum key shares in the hybrid key exchange [49].
- Robust hybrid systems, where multiple key exchange protocols are used in parallel to further reduce the attack surface [59].

Critically, all proposals to substitute the key exchange in the handshake of TLS are based on KEMs.

Another solution that provides both authenticity and secrecy of the TLS handshake, is a dedicated post-quantum authenticated key exchange protocol. Since post-quantum KEM public keys and ciphertexts are usually more compact than post-quantum public keys and signatures, in [52], KEMTLS has been proposed as an alternative to the TLS handshake. It uses an IND-CCA KEM for authentication instead of signatures. Specifically, it requires the ephemeral KEM to be IND-1CCA (indistinguishable under chosen ciphertext attack with 1 decapsulation query) secure. KEMTLS also provides PFS, ensuring that past communication sessions remain secure even if long-term keys are compromised in the future. For more information on the different combinations of KEMs that can be used in KEMTLS we refer to [52].

In [27], the authors show how to build an IND-qCCA KEM from any OW-CPA PKE in the ROM via an efficient Fujisaki-Okamoto (FO) transformation; moreover, they prove the security of an IND-1CCA KEM from an OW-CPA PKE in the QROM.

4 Experiments with PQ-TLS

| 4.1 Background work

In [55], we presented a detailed analysis of the performance of post-quantum TLS1.3. The main goal of this work was to better understand how these algorithms behave in the context of TLS and generate insights and best practices for their use. The experimental setup of this work was a highly isolated environment, in an effort to exclude outside factors that could influence the benchmark measurements during PQ-TLS1.3 handshakes.

In this report, we build on top of our previous efforts and we expand our measurements in a real 5G-core system. To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the first efforts to assess PQ-TLS in real telecommunication infrastructure. The scope here is to understand if PQC poses limitations to existing 5G infrastructure and as such, understand whether design choices need to be made as we move on to 6G systems. The rest of the chapter is organized as follows: in paragraph 4.2 we summarize briefly the main findings of our previous work, while in Section 4.3 we describe our design and testing methodology for PQC deployment in a 5G core system and we assess the test results.

| 4.2 Benchmarking Post-Quantum TLS1.3 [55]

In our previous study, a comprehensive methodology involving both black-box and white-box measurements to evaluate the performance of different PQC algorithms was employed [55]. Black-box measurements focus on handshake latency, capturing the overall time taken to establish a secure connection. White-box measurements delve into the computational costs of individual cryptographic operations, providing a granular understanding of performance bottlenecks. The experiments considered various network conditions, including different bandwidths, latencies, and packet loss rates, to assess the impact of network characteristics on PQC performance. This approach ensured a robust evaluation across diverse real-world scenarios. The measurement setup, illustrated in Figure 9 of the paper, involves a client and server exchanging cryptographic messages, with a timestamping recording precise timings.

Performance of Individual Algorithms. Several key encapsulation mechanisms and digital signature algorithms were evaluated including:

- Kyber: A lattice-based KEM demonstrating performance comparable to, and in some cases exceeding, existing pre-quantum algorithms. Its relatively small key and ciphertext sizes contribute to efficient handshakes.
- HQC: Another promising lattice-based KEM exhibiting competitive performance.
- Dilithium: A lattice-based signature algorithm that outperforms RSA in terms of speed, even at higher security levels. This makes it a strong candidate for post-quantum authentication.
- Falcon: A lattice-based signature scheme also showing favorable performance characteristics.

The results highlight the variability in performance across different PQC algorithms. While some, like Kyber and Dilithium, demonstrate clear advantages, others, like SPHINCS+, require further optimization. The paper provides detailed performance metrics for each algorithm, allowing for informed selection based on specific application requirements.

Figure 9: Experimental setup in D2.1 and in [55].

Hybrid Algorithms. The performance of hybrid algorithms, which combine classical and post-quantum cryptography, was also considered in D2.1 and in [55]. These hybrid approaches aim to provide robust security against both classical and quantum attacks during the transition period. *The results indicate that hybrid schemes do not introduce significant performance overhead, making them a viable option for immediate deployment.* An overall classification of the algorithms in terms of handshake latency is offered in Figure 10.

| 4.2.1 Insights

Several interesting insights were drawn from this work including:

- *PQC Readiness:* The study demonstrated that PQC is mature enough for integration into TLS 1.3 without substantial performance degradation. This dispels concerns about performance bottlenecks hindering PQC adoption.
- *Algorithm Selection:* The detailed performance analysis of individual algorithms provides valuable guidance for selecting the most suitable PQC scheme for specific applications and deployment scenarios.
- *Optimization Opportunities:* The research identifies areas where further optimization can enhance PQC performance, paving the way for even more efficient implementations.
- *Transition Strategy:* The results support a smooth transition to PQC, ensuring continued security and performance in the face of evolving threats.

Overall, the performance analysis demonstrated that PQC can be integrated into TLS 1.3 without compromising performance, and in some cases, even offering improvements. These findings encouraged further research and development in PQC; in fact, the analysis we offer in the next section for the introduction of PQC in a real 5G core system is a natural progression to our previous work.

| 4.3 PQC introduction in 5G core

The 5G system enabling connectivity to users and applications consists of various components primarily divided into Core Network components and Radio Network components. Core network components responsible for establishing connections for the user's devices communicate with each other using mutually authenticated TLS and HTTPS. Currently, the TLS uses classical ciphers for the protection of these messages. In this section, we describe the experiments performed in TNO's 5G-advanced testbed where classical TLS is replaced with a TLS version that uses post-quantum algorithms. The testbed is based on the open source 5G core implementation Open5GS [1] and contains several enhancements by TNO.

| 4.3.1 Methodology

In the context of 5G both symmetric and asymmetric key encryptions are used to secure the communication. Symmetric key encryption is used for encrypting the contents of communication

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Figure 10: KE (top) and SA (bottom) ranked depending on the logarithmic handshake latency.[55]

between UE (user equipment) and the base station. Since quantum computers are a threat to asymmetric key encryption schemes, we investigated places where they were used directly or indirectly.

| 4.3.2 TLS

HTTPS is used to secure communication between different network functions in the 5G core, which use service based architecture. HTTPS uses TLS to establish a secure session which internally uses asymmetric key encryption schemes. Since current TLS implementations are vulnerable to quantum computers, there is a need to use the quantum-safe versions of TLS.

| 4.3.3 IPsec

IPsec is used to secure the communication between base station, UPF and 5G core network. Like TLS, IPsec also uses asymmetric key encryption to establish a session between communicating parties. There is hence a need to have a quantum-safe version of IPsec that uses quantum-safe versions of asymmetric key encryption under the hood.

| 4.3.4 Identity protection

In the case of 5G, subscription identifiers are concealed and used for authentication. This is done with the help of elliptic key cryptography where public key of a home network is used by the device to encrypt its subscription identifier. This is discussed further in 3GPP TS 33.501.

| 4.4 Experiments

Within the context of 5G system, TLS is used between different components of the core network as a communication protection mechanism. These components referred to as Network Functions (NFs) are critical and carry out all the control plane traffic of all the users that are utilizing that network. We investigate the impact of enabling PQ-TLS versions in this context.

Our experimental setup and the tools used are described in Section 4.4.1. Metrics used for performance analysis is described in Section 4.4.2. In the 5G-advanced lab setup at TNO, all the Network Functions of 5G core were modified to enforce usage of quantum-safe fork of Open TLS. The process of creating this fork is described further in Section 4.4.3.

All the experiments are orchestrated automatically by an automated experiment orchestrator, to minimize human error in result gathering. The relevant processes are started on their respective hosts and the resulting generated data is gathered automatically. The data is stored along with the values of the parameters used during the experiment.

| 4.4.1 Experimental setup

The user device and Radio Access Network were simulated using the open-source tool UERAN-SIM [23] on an intel NUC with an Intel i7-8559U processor (4 cores, hyperthreaded). This tool was chosen since it was open source and it allows scripted simulation of large number of user

devices connecting to the core network. We ran the 5G core on a separate NUC machine with the same specifications where we run a set of 10 NFs (NRF, AMF, UPF, UDR, UDM, AUSF, NSSF, BSF, PCF, SMF). The two machines are connected over a 1Gbit/s LAN connection over which the traffic between the radio access node and a core network is routed. Upon starting the core network, algorithms for signature and KEM are configured on each of the network functions which are then used for the creation of TLS certificates and establishment of TLS sessions.

Figure 11: Experimental setup.

4.4.2 Performance Metrics

At regular intervals, the UEs send a registration request(1) followed by a PDU session creation request(2). In scenarios where there was no connection established prior to these request, the establishment of secure sessions between core network components was triggered because of the request from UEs.

Figure 12: Steps performed for performance metrics.

To analyze the impact of using the post-quantum version of TLS, Network functions were first provided with classical algorithms and the impact on latency and bandwidth between the components was recorded. These were then compared with the impact of various post-quantum algorithms that were supported by the library. Since the network functions were created at the beginning of each simulation, establishment of the sessions between them will be initiated upon receiving a request from the device to the network. This will give an ideal point to measure the impact on the system.

In case of a registration request, the time at which the request arrives at the AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function) (step 3 in Figure 13) was recorded as the starting point for measurements and the time at which the registration accept message leaves the AMF (step 21 in Figure 13) was chosen as the end point for measurements. The registration steps specified in 3GPP specifications TS 23.502 [3] is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Registration procedure between user device and 5G core network as specified in 3GPP TS 23.502 [3].

In the case of PDU session establishment, the time at which PDU session establishment request arrives at AMF (step 1 in Figure 14) was chosen as starting point of measurement, time at which PDU session response arrives at AMF (step 17 in Figure 14) was chosen as the end point of measurement. The entire procedure for PDU session establishment can be seen in Figure 14

Figure 14: PDU session establishment request and response between user device and 5G core network as specified in 3GPP TS 23.502 [3].

In both cases, timestamps at AMF were chosen the start and end point since it is the first entry/exit point of messages into the core network from the user's device and also in order to avoid any unexpected delays or latency added at the radio interface with the user's device and with AMF.

| 4.4.3 Enabling PQ-TLS in Open5GS

To enable the usage of PQ-TLS in the 5G core, following steps were performed:

1. `openssl` was compiled against `liboqs` [56] to enable the `oqsprovider`, granting access to PQ-TLS algorithms.
2. `libcurl` was compiled against the `oqsprovider-enabled openssl`.
3. `libnghttp2` was compiled against the `oqsprovider-enabled openssl`.
4. `open5gs` was compiled against these custom versions of `libcurl` and `libnghttp2`.
5. Changes were made to `open5gs`'s interface to `libcurl` and `libnghttp2` to be able to set KEM and signature algorithms as a parameter in the NFs.
6. For each signature algorithm in the `oqsprovider-enabled openssl`, a set of PKI certificates was generated.

Using the newly added configuration for KEM algorithm selection and using the existing certificate selection configuration options, it was possible to start an Open5GS core with any combination of KEM and signature algorithms.

| 4.5 Results

| 4.5.1 Scaling performance

We start by analyzing the performance of the 5G core and simulated radio setup. To do so, we run an experiment where we vary the number of active UEs. Each UE de-registers every 10 seconds, after which it immediately re-registers and requests a PDU session. An attempt is made to try to space out the re-registrations in time by starting the initial registrations for each UE t/n seconds apart, where t is the re-registration interval (10s) and n is the number of UEs. The 95th percentile for the PDU session setup durations can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15: PDU setup duration scaling considering 95th percentile.

Both a classical algorithm selection and a post-quantum algorithm selection are tested. We can see that there is a distinct jump in the 95th percentile starting at 40 UEs. The jump is roughly 200ms and resembles some periodic queue batching mechanism. There are various timers in the UERANSIM software, some of which had a default value of 200ms, but altering the UERANSIM source code to change these timers had no effect on the results. Analyzing these results with the assumption of some unidentified batching mechanism in mind, we see a linear increase in the 95th percentiles. We have observed more jumps (up to 400ms, 600ms, etc.) at higher UE counts and higher percentiles, but many of these are the result of the system as a whole failing. Increasing the number of UEs to 130 UEs and further led to unpredictable behaviour such as UE requests being ignored by the core/RAN, errors and warnings being triggered in the core etc. We have therefore chosen to limit our results to 120 UEs. There is no clear difference between the classical and post-quantum algorithms, even when looking at the higher percentiles. However, it is important that if outliers are considered, the results of each algorithm selection diverge quite a bit and the usage of post-quantum algorithms would lead to poor experience in such rare cases. This can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16: PDU setup duration scaling considering the outliers.

4.5.2 KEM and signature algorithms

We investigate separately the impact of using PQ KEM and PQ signature algorithms. We use a selection of 4 algorithms for each. One of these will be the classical algorithms used by default by Open5GS, and the other three were chosen to represent low, middle and high-impact algorithms based on [55]. The selection is also influenced by the following factors:

- We expect hybrid algorithms to be the most likely to be adopted and limit our selection to those.
- Where possible, we select standardized versions.

We evaluated the performance of the core by comparing PDU session setup duration (incl. prerequisite registration) across our algorithm selections. The number of UEs is fixed at 70. All tests were repeated 10 times. The results can be seen in Figure 17 and Figure 18.

Figure 17: eCDF of PDU session setup duration varying KEM algorithms with fixed classical signature algorithm.

Figure 18: eCDF of PDU session setup duration varying signature algorithms with fixed classical KEM.

All KEM algorithms perform very similarly, with minimal, though observable, service-level impact when scaling to heavier PQ-TLS KEM algorithms. The more lightweight p256_bike1 even slightly outperforms the classical secp256r1. We see different behavior for the signature algo-

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rithms. The results are very close together except for the very heaviest `sphincsha2128` algorithm, which performs consistently worse. We suspected that this was largely due to the delays incurred by the increase in data volume required to set up the TLS connections. This impact on data volume can be seen in Figure 19 and Figure 20.

Figure 19: Data volumes for a single PDU session setup varying KEM algorithms with fixed classical signature algorithm.

Figure 20: Data volumes for a single PDU session setup varying signature algorithms with fixed classical KEM.

These experiments were executed with the core network and radio network and with a single device (UE). Data volumes of the SBI interfaces for each NF were measured. For the signature algorithms, we see a clear correlation between the worse-performing algorithms in the previous section and the higher-volume algorithms here. However, there is also a large difference in data volumes for the KEM algorithms, where we did not see a large effect on PDU session setup durations. Data volumes alone cannot therefore explain the difference in results.

The phenomenon, that the initial handshake seems to be causing most of the tail-end of the PDU session setup duration distribution for the high-impact algorithms, can be seen when we plot the PDU session setup duration against core run-time. See Figure 21.

Figure 21: PDU session setup durations over time.

4.5.3 Conclusion

Our results illustrate that enabling PQ-TLS KEM and signature algorithms in the Open5GS 5G core has minimal impact, other than the tested SPHINCS+ algorithm, which impacts the tail end of PDU session setup duration distribution poorly. For the other tested algorithms the main impact observed is in the outliers (rarely occurring events at 99.5+ percentile). In all cases the poor results are obtained immediately after the core starts. Our findings for most cases can be summarized by Table 3, where we consider middle-impact (as per our measurements) PQ algorithms and compare them against the classical counterparts. In this table, the term “UE setup duration” refers to the total time of the registration procedure plus the total time of the PDU session setup procedure. The term “SBI data rate” refers to the average total data rate across all the SBI interfaces in the core network during the test.

Algorithms	UE setup duration		SBI data rate
	Median	99th percentile	
(secp256r1, rsaEncryption)	257 ms	505 ms	111.0 KB/s
(p384_bike13, p384_mldsa65)	264 ms	669 ms	114.8 KB/s
(p384_bike13, rsaEncryption)	260 ms	571 ms	112.5 KB/s
(secp256r1, p384_mldsa65)	260 ms	507 ms	115.2 KB/s

Table 3: Summary results of the PQ-TLS enabled Open5GS experiments.

4.6 Future work

Identity protection in the case of 5G that was mentioned in 4.3.4 could be a potential area where protection mechanisms based on post-quantum algorithms could be explored. Similar to TLS, interfaces where IPsec is used in 5G as mentioned in 4.3.3 could be modified for the usage of IPsec versions that could support post-quantum algorithms,

5 Updates on PQC Standardisation and Regulation Efforts

The main standardisation effort in the domain of post-quantum cryptography is led by NIST, the US National Institute of Science and Technology¹. In some sense, NIST will provide the de facto global standards – as they have for other areas in cryptography, including the SHA algorithms for hashing and the AES block cipher and its predecessors. Therefore, the bulk of this chapter focuses on describing the different standardisation efforts led by NIST.

Below, we will discuss the state of NIST’s post-quantum initiatives. Firstly, we will discuss the stateful hash-based schemes that were approved in 2020. Then, we will discuss the four finalists that were selected for standardisation as a result of NIST’s Post Quantum Standardisation Process in 2022. Thirdly, we will discuss the Round 4 candidates that also resulted from this process. Then, we will discuss what has been dubbed the “signature onramp”: a newer effort, again led by NIST, focused solely on selecting additional post-quantum digital signature algorithms for standardisation. This subsection will be the most in-depth, as it is the most recent development and is very relevant for the future of TLS and thus networking more generally. Lastly, subsection 5.5 will cover other, i.e. non-NIST, developments in the standardisation and regulatory space around post-quantum cryptography.

| 5.1 Stateful Hash-based Signature Schemes

The first documents that NIST published in the domain of post-quantum cryptography were not directly related to the primary standardisation process that started in 2016 and the fourth round of which is still ongoing. In parallel to that process, NIST already approved some signature schemes with specific properties and applications: XMSS and LMS, as well as their multi-tree variants XMSS-MT and HSS [42]. In fact, rather than developing these standards from scratch, NIST considered these schemes as developed by the Internet Research Task Force [26, 35].

XMSS and LMS (and their multi-tree variants) are so-called *stateful* schemes. In particular, stateful hash-based schemes can produce a limited amount of signatures, and for each signature, there is a private key. The *state* of the scheme is the collection of all private keys along with the information which keys have already been used, because reusing one of the private keys leads to security risks. This means that during deployment and use, this state needs to be monitored very carefully at all times, and mismanagement of the state can have dire consequences for security. Thus, stateful schemes are only suitable for specific scenarios, where the use of the private key (i.e. the state) can be controlled very carefully. So, while XMSS and LMS were good candidates for early standardisation, they do not cover all that is needed. The inherent statefulness of these schemes means that they are not suitable for general use.

| 5.2 NIST PQC Standardisation Process: the Winners

In D2.1 of this CONFIDENTIAL6G project, titled Post-Quantum Analysis Report, a detailed and technical overview was presented for the NIST PQC winners Kyber, Dilithium and SPHINCS+. We refer to that deliverable for a technical treatment of those algorithms. The present deliverable does not aim to reiterate or summarise those descriptions. Rather, it seeks to place them in the broader context of NIST’s PQC efforts.

In 2016, NIST kicked off their Post-Quantum Standardisation Process with a call for proposals. In particular, the goal of this process was to standardise key encapsulation mechanisms (KEMs) as well as digital signature algorithms (DSAs). After three rounds of this process, which was organised like a competition, four schemes were selected for standardisation in 2022: the KEM Kyber, and the DSAs Dilithium, Falcon and SPHINCS+. After about two years of additional tweaks and minor updates, the standards for Kyber, Dilithium and SPHINCS+ were published by NIST in

¹<https://csrc.nist.gov/Projects/post-quantum-cryptography/post-quantum-cryptography-standardization>

August 2024, under the new names ML-KEM [37], ML-DSA [38] and SLH-DSA [39], respectively. A draft standard for the fourth winner, Falcon, is yet to be published but is expected soon at the time of writing (December 2024). Falcon will be standardised under the name FN-DSA.

Kyber and Dilithium were developed as part of the same project: CRYSTALS, which is an acronym for Cryptographic Suite for Algebraic Lattices. Indeed, both of these algorithms rely on certain mathematical problems around structured lattices for their security. These so-called *module lattices* are also the reason for the ML in the standardised names ML-KEM and ML-DSA. NIST expects these two algorithms to work well in most applications.

Falcon relies on structured lattices as well: its to-be-standard name FN-DSA refers to “FFT over NTRU-lattices”. Falcon has smaller signatures than ML-DSA, which may be advantageous in certain applications. However, Falcon uses floating point arithmetic, which is difficult to implement securely.

The letters SLH in the new name for SPHINCS+ stand for “Stateless hash-based”. Indeed, SPHINCS+ can be seen as the evolution of XMSS and LMS, where the issue of statefulness has been mitigated.

While standardisation of these candidates is definitely a sign of progress, it is not the end of the story. Firstly, there is only one standardised KEM, while specific use cases may leave space for other KEMs with different properties. Secondly, there is quite a heavy reliance on lattice problems for security: of the four standards, only SLH-DSA is not based on structured lattices. Indeed, should some cryptanalytic advance render lattice cryptography insecure, then ML-KEM, ML-DSA and FN-DSA would all be vulnerable. SLH-DSA is a more conservative choice in terms of security, as it only relies on certain security properties of hash functions which are well-understood. However, SLH-DSA has quite a large signature and its signing time is also significantly worse than the alternatives.

All in all, the cryptographic community tends to agree that additional algorithms should be standardised to allow for more diversity in performance and security assumptions. For this reason, two standardisation tracks are currently still running. Firstly, one or more additional KEMs will be standardised as a result of Round 4, which is a direct continuation of the standardisation process that led to the four winners discussed above. We will discuss this in 5.3. Secondly, additional signatures are expected to be standardised as part of a new process kicked off in 2023, as discussed in 5.4

5.3 NIST PQC Standardisation Process: Round 4

As NIST announced in 2022 which algorithms were selected for standardisation at the end of round 3 (i.e. Kyber, Dilithium, Falcon and SPHINCS+), they also announced a number of algorithms that would proceed to round 4. All four algorithms proceeding to round 4 were KEMs: the isogeny-based SIKE and the three code-based schemes Classic McEliece, HQC and BIKE. The idea is that one or more of these algorithms could be standardised to diversify security assumptions for KEM and/or to serve specific use cases.

The isogeny-based SIKE was broken by an advance in cryptanalysis [13], so that all remaining algorithms in Round 4 are code-based KEMs. Classic McEliece is the most conservative of the three. Its security is well understood and no impactful attacks were found since its inception in 1978. The main disadvantage of Classic McEliece is the very large size of its public key, which can run into the megabytes. HQC and BIKE both introduce extra structure in their underlying codes. While this allows the schemes to have a smaller public key than Classic McEliece, it comes at the cost of possible attacks exploiting this additional structure. NIST expects to standardise at most one of HQC and BIKE as an alternative to ML-KEM for general-purpose use. Classic McEliece may be standardised as a conservative backup for specific use-cases.

| 5.4 NIST PQC Standardisation Process: Additional Signatures

As discussed above, NIST's 2022 announcement of the winners was accompanied by the news of a Round 4 for several algorithms. However, this fourth round does not include any signature schemes. Since both Falcon (FN-DSA) and Dilithium (ML-DSA) are based on structured lattices and SPHINCS+ (SLH-DSA) is not suitable for all use cases, the selected signature schemes are not diverse in terms of underlying security assumptions. Thus, NIST published a "Call for Additional Digital Signature Schemes for the Post-Quantum Cryptography Standardisation Process " in September 2022. In particular, the call argues that²:

"NIST is primarily interested in additional general-purpose signature schemes that are not based on structured lattices. For certain applications, such as certificate transparency, NIST may also be interested in signature schemes that have short signatures and fast verification. NIST is open to receiving additional submissions based on structured lattices, but is intent on diversifying the post-quantum signature standards. As such, any structured lattice-based signature proposal would need to significantly outperform CRYSTALS-Dilithium and FALCON in relevant applications and/or ensure substantial additional security properties to be considered for standardization."

Based on this call, NIST received a total of 50 submissions, 40 of which were considered full and proper. In October 2024, NIST published a technical report [43] in which it was announced that 14 candidates would proceed to Round 2. In what follows, we put these 14 algorithms in some context by grouping them by the type of cryptography that underlies them. Additionally, we discuss some advantages and disadvantages of different schemes. For additional or more detailed reading, we refer to the submission documents from the different candidates as received by NIST [40], NIST's own report [43] as well a write-up by experts from Cloudflare [9].

| 5.4.1 Lattice-based

As noted earlier, NIST has already elected to standardise Dilithium (ML-DSA) and Falcon (FN-DSA), both of which are lattice-based digital signature schemes. While NIST is open to lattice-based submissions, but these would have to outperform Dilithium (ML-DSA) and Falcon (FN-DSA) significantly or have different (additional) security properties.

HAWK is the only lattice-based scheme that has progressed to Round 2. In some sense, HAWK can be seen as a variation on or successor to Falcon (hence the similarity in the name) due to similarities in the design, but with two major differences. Firstly, HAWK does not require floating-point arithmetic, the need for which is generally considered a disadvantage of Falcon. Secondly, HAWK relies on certain relatively new security assumptions around lattices, which have not been studied particularly well.

| 5.4.2 Code-based

As discussed in 5.3, NIST will likely standardise one or two code-based KEMs after round 4. Code-based cryptography has been around for a while and is therefore generally considered on the more conservative end in terms of security. Two signature schemes based on codes have progressed to the second round of the call for additional signatures. **LESS** is based on the Linear Equivalence problem (in fact, LESS stands for Linear Equivalence Signature Scheme), which is also a traditional and well-understood problem in coding theory. **CROSS** is based on a newer variant of a well-studied security assumption. LESS has (very) large public keys and both LESS and CROSS have large signature sizes. Of the two, CROSS has the better overall performance (i.e. smaller and faster), but has the disadvantage of relying on a less well-studied security assumption.

²<https://csrc.nist.gov/csrc/media/Projects/pqc-dig-sig/documents/call-for-proposals-dig-sig-sept-2022.pdf>

| 5.4.3 Multivariate

Multivariate cryptography is based on the hardness of solving systems of multivariate polynomial equations. Several generations of multivariate signature schemes exist, and in fact a scheme called Rainbow was a Round-3 finalist in the main NIST standardisation procedure described above. However, Rainbow was unexpectedly broken in 2022 [11].

Four multivariate schemes have been announced to progress to the next round. **UOV**, for *Unbalanced Oil and Vinegar* is an older multivariate system that has been studied for more than 25 years. UOV is very fast and has small signatures, but its public key is by far the largest among all candidates. Several proposals have been made to mitigate this large public key size. Indeed, the three other multivariate schemes, **QR-UOV**, **MAYO** and **SNOVA**, all introduce some additional mathematical structure which allows for smaller public keys. However, such extra structure may be exploited for attacks. Indeed, some attacks on these three schemes or related schemes exist. Although the underlying multivariate problem has not directly been attacked, these attacks and the breaking of Rainbow (which also introduced extra structure for the same reason), make it so that the security of multivariate schemes is generally considered less conservative than some other approaches.

| 5.4.4 MPC-in-the-head

MPC-in-the-head is a cryptographic paradigm for digital signature schemes that is quickly growing in popularity. Indeed, in 2017 only 1 of 23 submissions for signature schemes that NIST received for the main PQC standardisation effort was MPC-in-the-head. For the 2022 call for additional signatures, 6 of the 50 schemes were in this paradigm. In fact, all of these 6 will proceed to the next round: MIRA and MiRitH will merge into **Mirath**; the other schemes are called **MQOM**, **PERK**, **RYDE** and **SDitH**.

While the specifics of these schemes differ significantly, the overarching idea of MPC-in-the-head remains the same. MPC, or *multi-party computation*, is a large subfield of cryptography where different parties can collaborate to calculate some function on their collective data *without revealing* their data to each other. We refer to the upcoming Deliverable 2.3 from the CONFIDENTIAL6G project for a larger background on MPC. In the MPC-in-the-head paradigm, the signing party simulates an MPC protocol with several virtual parties. To verify a signature, the verifier is given access to some intermediate calculations of some of the virtual parties: “enough so that none of the parties could have cheated on any of the steps, but not enough that it allows the verifier to figure out [the secret value] x themselves” [9].

These five schemes have somewhat similar performance: public key sizes are relatively small, signature sizes are quite big and verification and signing speeds are mediocre. As the paradigm is relatively new, improvements may occur and additional analysis is required for some of the underlying problems as well.

| 5.4.5 Isogeny-based

Isogeny-based cryptography is a relatively new field compared to most other paradigms, which also produced the KEM SIKE as discussed in 5.3. While SIKE was broken, that attack does not apply to the signature scheme **SQISign**, which will proceed to Round 2 of the additional signature call. The main advantage of SQISign are the small key and signatures sizes. The biggest disadvantage of SQISign is the fact that it is slow. In fact, both signing and verifying are orders of magnitude slower than most other candidates.

| 5.4.6 Symmetric-based

The last scheme, known as **FAEST**, is based on the so-called *vector oblivious linear evaluation in the head* (VOLE-in-the-head) paradigm. FAEST is conceptually related to MPC-in-the-head but instead bases its security on the security of AES. FAEST’s performance is similar to but better

than the related MPC-in-the-head signature schemes. The main disadvantage is the novelty and complexity of the construction, with the underlying idea being as recent as 2023 [10].

| 5.5 Other Efforts around Standardisation and Regulation

Besides the initiatives by NIST, there are many other standardisation and regulatory bodies involved with PQC.

ISO and IEC have presented stateful digital signatures schemes in ISO/IEC 14888-4, namely XMSS, XMSS-MT LMS and HSS, which also have been adopted by NIST [31, 42]. ISO is also working on an update of ISO/IEC 18033-2 to include PQC key encapsulation mechanisms [30], where Classic McEliece and FrodoKEM might also be standardised.

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) has many working groups working on integrating PQC, an overview of which can be found at [2]. In particular, this includes work on TLS and IPsec.

In Europe, the ETSI Cybersecurity (CYBER) and Quantum-Safe Cryptography (QSC) committees have published recommendations on the use of PQC [29].

The Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA) has published several guidelines for quantum risk management and PQC migration in different use cases in telecommunications [20, 21].

There are also many regulations related to cyber security. Some do not take PQC explicitly into account, but do require applying cryptography that provides sufficient protection against state-of-the-art attackers, which, in the future, may include quantum computers. Some examples of these regulations are the European Union Network and Information Systems (NIS2) directive [19], General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and European Electronic Communications Code (EECC), as well as the United States Federal Information Security Modernization Act (FISMA), United States White House Memorandum and Commercial National Security Algorithm Suite (CNSA) [41].

6 Strategy and Insights for the PQC-Migration

In this section, we consider general insights and strategies for the migration to post-quantum cryptography. We note that within the CONFIDENTIAL6G project, deliverable 2.1 also contains material on the transition to PQC. However, where those contributions focus on the challenges and concerns, the present section aims to provide strategic insights. Parts of this section are heavily inspired by The PQC Migration Handbook [5].

In the following sections, we will first present a high-level overview of the three-step migration strategy. Then, in Section 6.2, we will list a number of *no-regret moves* and consider some in more detail. Section 6.3 zooms in and considers some migration priorities for 5G/6G networks, as particularly relevant to the CONFIDENTIAL6G project.

| 6.1 Migration strategy

For the migration to PQC, a three-step approach is recommended: diagnosis, planning and execution. Especially in the first step, many suggested actions are useful independently of development of quantum computers and are therefore dubbed *no-regret moves*. Below, we elaborate on these three steps and no-regret moves. Note that they are also described in more detail in the PQC Migration Handbook [5].

As a first step, a vulnerability diagnosis should be made. The urgency with which migration actions should be taken differs per organisation and depends, among others, on the kind of data involved, possible threats, and relations with other organisations. To get a clear overview of this, inventories of cryptographic assets, handled data, and suppliers should be made. Even if the urgency for migration actions is low, these inventories can already be made, as it is generally good knowledge to have within an organisation, especially when kept up to date. For instance, a cryptographic inventory is also useful to prevent data leaks and to monitor compliance with rules, regulations and policies. With this information, a *quantum risk assessment* can be performed. As described in [5], this risk assessment is based on the weaknesses of cryptographic algorithms against quantum computers, the impact of a breach and the effort and time required for migrating.

The second step consists of planning: when and how to migrate. The moment to start migrating is largely based on Mosca's inequality: $X + Y < Z$, where X is the time an asset must remain secure, Y is the time it takes to migrate and Z is the time left until the creation of a cryptographically relevant quantum computer. Clearly, if $X + Y > Z$, there is a security risk.

Based on the urgency of migration, certified PQC libraries may or may not already be available. To obtain some assurances, the use of hybrid solutions, as described in D2.1, is highly recommended. The rest of the planning consists of determining whether cryptographic assets should be replaced, if so, by what, and the order in which this migration should take place. In this planning, both business processes, like personnel, facilities and finances, and technical considerations, like dependencies, hardware replacement, and testing, should be taken into account.

The final step in this three-step process is the actual execution of the migration. In particular, the use of crypto-agile and hybrid solutions as described in D2.1 is recommended.

Note that these three steps are not to be taken completely sequentially for the organisation as a whole. Instead, an organisation may start performing these steps for the most critical parts and later, possibly in parallel, work on migrating other parts of their infrastructure. That is, an organisation may in practice be conducting different steps at the same time, but for different parts of the IT-infrastructure.

| 6.2 No-regret moves

The uncertainty around the timeframe for a cryptographically relevant quantum computer, combined with the fact that PQC is a very active area of research, may cause uncertainty as to when to

start a PQC migration. Procrastination may involve large risks. Therefore, some no-regret moves can already be taken that are valuable to any organisation. This includes the following moves, mostly from the first migration step (diagnosis):

- Assessment of supply chain dependencies. This concerns both vendors on which an organisation relies, as well as others that are impacted by cryptographic decisions of an organisation, who should be known in order to align their PQC migration strategy.
- Establishment of cryptographic asset management. For cryptographic agility, a good overview that helps identifying and resolving vulnerabilities in cryptographic implementations is necessary to reduce incident response times.
- Review of cryptographic policies. Developments in technology and regulation may require changes to these policies.
- Execution of a risk assessment. The incorporation of a quantum threat will help determine when and how to migrate to PQC.
- Estimation of migration costs. This includes financial and capacity constraints for a migration.
- Inventory of regulatory requirements. In order to comply, updates from standardisation and regulatory bodies that are publishing new requirements related to PQC should be taken into account.
- Creation of a backup plan in case of a broken cryptographic algorithm (implementation). This will help to continue business and avoid down-time.
- Collaboration with peers. This is important in order to share experiences and provide interoperability.

Here, we highlight the process around the establishment of cryptographic asset management.

6.2.1 Cryptographic asset management

The first phase of cryptographic asset management is the identification of cryptographic policies that are already in place in an organisation. One could think of policies that guide the life cycle of cryptographic keys or the specification of what (versions of) protocols to use. Further, it needs to be understood what regulations and standards to comply with, which may be sector or region-dependent. This will help locate and prioritise cryptographic assets.

Up next is the creation of a cryptographic inventory: a complete overview of all cryptographic assets within the organisation. Such an inventory is created through the process of cryptographic discovery: a search or scan throughout an organisation's IT-infrastructure looking to identify any cryptographic assets. First, a strategy for cryptographic discovery needs to be defined. This includes objectives, scope, discovery methodology, type of data required, reporting and reviewing. With this information, the asset discovery can be executed. This concerns the analysis of e.g. software that is being developed, operational systems and applications, filesystems and network traffic.

To manage an inventory of used cryptography, a standardised format is recommended. The CycloneDX Bill of Materials standard supports the specification of a Cryptographic Bill of Materials (CBOM), mostly focused on software and less on e.g. network traffic. It gives a basis on what type of information to collect for different assets, as well as a way to track dependencies between them. An example of an automated way to integrate CBOMs can be found in the static code analysis engine CodeQL, which allows for the conversion of its output to a valid CBOM. However, automatic tooling does not generally give an all-encompassing overview: tracking some specific

elements like IVs and passwords, as well as key management procedures, is often not supported. Therefore, automatic tooling along with manual effort is useful for a thorough asset discovery process.

When the initial cryptographic discovery has been completed and a cryptographic inventory has been formed, it is important to keep the inventory up to date. This way, the right information is available to determine needed actions.

| 6.3 Migration priorities for 5G/6G networks

Developing a strategy for a smooth migration to PQC is not a "one-size-fits-all" type of process and there are several factors that need to be considered during decision-making. Moreover, different organizations have different requirements and timelines to respect, making the overall migration discussion rather complex. In this paragraph we attempt to bring some structure to the problem, so that stakeholders can make informed decisions.

A logical order of implementation of quantum-safe technology should focus on the threats posed by QCs. The current Harvest-Now-Decrypt-Later threat essentially requires protecting stored data and data-in-flight. Therefore, in the first phase of migration, quantum-safety features in telecom networks should focus on the data/user plane, making harvesting of in-flight data useless. In transport networks, there is typically an extensive use of symmetric cryptography and as such, we can already assume quantum-safety for data-in-flight. These can be used for example in data-center inter-connectivity, backhaul of fixed and mobile network traffic in more central parts of the network (incl. mm-wave mobile backhaul), and even last-mile applications for government using dedicated optics CPEs (Customer Premises Equipment).

In access networks, parts running on transport functionality (e.g., aggregation) can in principle benefit from the same symmetric quantum-safe data-plane mechanisms. Regarding the last mile user link, fixed and mobile access networks differ a bit. Fixed networks (Passive Optical Networks - PON) already use symmetric encryption today, and the latest PON standard (G.hsp) allows to support 256-bit quantum-safe key sizes. However, the key exchange and related authentication mechanisms need to be updated and can in principle leverage pre-shared keys. Mobile networks (5G/6G RAN), on the other hand, require a Public Key Infrastructure and therefore have a strong dependency on 3GPP's PQC standardization.

A second phase would be to evolve into a fully quantum-resilient network. This would require addressing the security mechanisms used in the management and the control-signaling planes, such that the operation of the network is safeguarded. The management plane should be addressed before the control-signaling plane because it is more exposed (through its external interfaces), it includes network & security management systems, and moreover has a weaker dependency on standardization. The control-signaling plane PQC adoption will mostly – and necessarily – need to follow timelines from Standardization organizations. Note that these considerations apply largely to 5G networks which have the need to migrate, whereas in 6G the current consensus is that, starting from 3GPP Rel.21, 6G should be considered quantum safe by default.

With respect to Confidential6G, the project will substitute any asymmetric cryptography used in 5G with algorithms that resist attacks by quantum computers (where applicable), where algorithms to achieve confidentiality have the highest urgency as mentioned before.

| 6.4 Dissemination

To disseminate our conceptual findings (Section 2) and initiate discussions in the community, we have reached out to the main platform for the further development of the TLS protocol, the IETF TLS mailing list on June 24th, 2024: https://mailarchive.ietf.org/arch/msg/tls/51EbKkEKBgJJdyFZoGnsNfLu_hag/. In particular, we were interested in the question of whether existing libraries used by major TLS library developers provide simple access to the underlying IND-CPA secure PKE used in Kyber implementations. While generally Kyber.CCAKEM always

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uses Kyber.CPAPKE due to the Fujisaki-Okamoto transform (and thus implementations of Kyber.CCAKEM always include implementations of Kyber.CPAPKE), it is not clear to us whether our conceptual improvements can be implemented explicitly easily when designing new protocols. At the same time we want to bring this topic to the attention of library developers so that they may decide on improving interfaces to their cryptographic algorithms that allow us implement our ideas more easily.

Dimitrios Schoinianakis is co-developing Internet draft <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-pquip-pqc-engineers/> of the IETF that explains why engineers need to be aware of and understand post-quantum cryptography, detailing the impact of post-quantum computers on existing systems and the challenges involved in transitioning. This generally helps to disseminate parts of the findings reflected in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 to the broader public.

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7 Impact on Climate Change

The impact of the findings in Deliverable 2.2 on climate change mirrors Deliverable 2.1.

We note that the efficiency goals in cryptography generally *align* well with the efforts to reduce the negative impact of technology on climate change. Higher efficiency allows to consume less energy for the same computational task. This saves valuable resources. This particularly holds for our conceptual contribution. Since the described protocol improvements have the potential to be used more broadly and since they also apply to other algorithms besides Kyber, they bear the potential to widely increase the efficiency of PQ-secure AKE protocols used in practice. The described benefits predominantly allow computational savings as compared with a naïve application of IND-CCA secure KEMs in AKE protocols. Overall savings can be considerable in practice, how frequent AKE protocols are executed in practice. The content delivery network Cloudflare alone reports 15 million TLS connections per second³, which gives $1.2 \cdot 10^{12}$ connections per day.

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³<https://blog.cloudflare.com/another-look-at-pq-signatures/>

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